

Family of Kaniadakis-Like Distributions?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 8, 2026

It seems that the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions require that for $x = -e_i/T \ll 1$, $p(x)$ becomes a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution, while for $x \gg 1$, the distribution is $C x^{-1/k}$, or $1/(1-q)$ in the Tsallis case. We have suggested in (1) that a further requirement present is the average of moments. In particular, if the constraints (used in a MaxEnt process) are a set of average moments, then these represent the full statistical information about the physical system and $p(x)$ $F(p(x))$ (the entropy) is also of the form of an average and cannot represent any more moment averages. If one has $\langle e_i \rangle$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$, then $F(p(x)) = a + bx$, which is the case for the MB, Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions. From this, we try to show that the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions must become the MB one for $x \ll 1$. In (2), we have argued that the Kaniadakis entropy $p(x) F(p(x))$ does not maximize entropy with respect to the constraints $\langle x \rangle$ and $\sum_i p(x) = 1$ because a special bridge function is required (namely $\sqrt{1 + kx}$) which transitions to $1 + .5kx$ for $x \ll 1$ and to kx for $x \gg 1$.

Here we suggest that one may create a family of Kaniadakis like distributions if these are only the requirements needed. In particular, we suggest that:

$$p(x) = \left\{ kx + \sum_{n=2, N} \left[a_n + \frac{1}{(n-1)!} (kx)^n \right]^{1/n} \right\}^{1/k} \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{with } a_n = \left[\frac{1}{(N-n+1)!} \right]^{1/n} \quad ((2))$$

Again, such a family of distributions will not maximize an entropy described by $p(x) F(p(x))$ where $F(p(x)) = a + bx$ (because only two average moments are used as constraints).

The Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis Distributions

The MB, Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions are the same in the $x = -e_i/T \ll 1$ limit. We argue that this follows from constraint $\langle x \rangle$ and $\sum_i p(x) = 1$ and the entropy form:

$$p(x)F(p(x)) \quad \text{where } F(p(x)) = a + bx \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is argued to hold in (1) because if constraints represent a statistical description of the physical system and $p(x)F$, also being an average may be expanded in terms of x and should not represent more average moments, otherwise there is inconsistency. We argue that it is ((3)) which forces these three distributions to be the same for $x \ll 1$.

$$\text{Consider: } F(p) = a + bx \quad \text{For } x \ll 1 \quad p(x) = c + dx \quad \text{and } F(p) = a + b_1 p \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Let the constraint be: } xp + b_3 p. \quad \text{Then: } F + p \frac{dF}{dp} = x + b_3$$

$$\text{Thus: } b = x \quad ((5)) \quad \text{in general.}$$

For the MB case: $F(p) = \ln(\exp(x)/C) = 1 + x - \ln(C)$ ((6))

The unnormalized Tsallis and Kaniadakis forms should also match the MB for $x \ll 1$.

For $x \gg 1$, we consider only distributions which have the form:

$C(k) x^{\text{power } 1/k}$ ((7))

$p(x) = \{ f(x) \}^{\text{power } 1/k}$ such that the two limits of x are satisfied ((8)).

The simplest solution is: $f(x) = 1 + kx$ ((9))

and this is in fact the Tsallis solution. There is no function which bridges the two limits and the Tsallis scenario respects maximization of entropy. It is possible, however, to have a more complicated solution (matching $\exp(x)$ to higher order using a bridging function such as:

$\sqrt{1+kx}$ ((10))

For $x \ll 1$, $\sqrt{1+kx} \rightarrow 1 + .5kx$ while for $x \gg 1$, it tends to kx ((11))

If there is a bridging function, however, there is extra information in the problem and we argued in (2) that $p(x)F(p)$ is not maximized subject to constraints. The distribution using the bridge function ((10) is called a Kaniadakis distribution with:

$p(x) = \{ \sqrt{1+kx} + kx \}^{\text{power } 1/k}$ ((12))

and $F(p) = 1/2k \{ p^{\text{power } k} - p^{\text{power } -k} \}$ ((13))

We suggest that if one is only interested in the two limits $x \ll 1$ matching an MB distribution and $x \gg 1$ matching a power law, then one may create a family of Kaniadakis like distributions, each one approximating $\exp(x)$ to a higher order for $x \ll 1$, while retaining a power law $C x^{\text{power } 1/k}$ for $x \gg 1$.

Kaniadakis-Like Family of Distributions

As noted above, if one only requires $p(x)$ to match the MB case at $x \ll 1$ and $x^{\text{power } 1/k}$ for $x \gg 1$, then there could be multiple bridge functions instead of simply ((10)). The simplest case would be to extend to:

$p(x) = \{ \sqrt{a_1+kx} + [a_2 + .5kkx]^{\text{power } 1/3} + kx \}^{\text{power } 1/k}$ ((14))

For $x \ll 1$, $1 = \sqrt{a_1} + a_2^{\text{power } 1/3}$ ((15))

To have both have equal weight: $\sqrt{a_1} = 1/2$ and $1/2 = a_2^{\text{power } 1/3}$ ((16))

We suggest that one may generalize the above idea to:

$$p(x) = \left\{ kx + \sum_{n=2}^N \left[a_n + \frac{1}{(n-1)!} (kx)^n \right]^{1/n} \right\}^{1/k} \quad ((17))$$

$$\text{with } a_n = \left[\frac{1}{(N-n+1)!} \right]^{1/n} \quad ((18))$$

In other words, we suggest that one could seek other Kaniadakis like distributions in nature. We note, however, that in this general case, it is not simple to express $F(p)$.

Conclusion

The Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions approximate the Maxwell-Boltzmann for $x = -e_i/T \ll 1$ and become $C (kx)^{1/k}$ for $x \gg 1$. The simplest way to satisfy both x limits is to use $p(x) = f(x)^{1/k}$ with $f(x) = 1+kx$. In such a case, there is a simple $1+kx$ function and no bridge function is needed for intermediate x values. It is, however, possible to introduce a bridge function such as $\sqrt{1+kx}$ into $p(x) = \left\{ kx + \sqrt{1+kx} \right\}^{1/k}$. This bridge function has the appropriate behaviour in both limits, but we argue in (2) that this represents extra information and so this case, the Kaniadakis one cannot maximize entropy given by $p(x)$ $F(p(x))$ such that $F(p) = a+bx$.

Here we introduce a family of Kaniadakis-like distributions which also satisfy the two x limits, i.e.

$$p(x) = \left\{ kx + \sum_{n=2}^N \left[a_n + \frac{1}{(n-1)!} (kx)^n \right]^{1/n} \right\}^{1/k}$$

$$\text{with } a_n = \left[\frac{1}{(N-n+1)!} \right]^{1/n}$$

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. M (preprint, zenodo, 2026)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Kaniadakis Entropy, The Notion of Moments and MaxEnt at $e/T \ll 1$ and $e/T \gg 1$ (preprint, zenodo, 2026)